

MAGIC AND SUPERSTITION IN THE WORLDVIEW OF LATVIAN PEASANTS (16TH-18TH CENTURIES)

Version 1

Description

The project focuses on the ideas of Latvian peasants about the world around them and their place in it, which are explored through the analysis of magical rituals and superstitions widespread in this social group in the 16th - 18th centuries. Magic is rituals associated with belief in a person's ability to supernaturally influence people, animals, natural phenomena, as well as imaginary spirits and gods. In turn, superstition is understood as belief in the miraculous, supernatural, belief in cause and effect, where a cause-and-effect relationship is not visible. The project examines the following issues: factors that influenced the formation of magical rituals and superstitions; belief in miracles; ideas about the earthly and otherworldly worlds; man in the earthly and otherworldly worlds; nature in superstitions and magic; magical rituals, and superstitions in everyday life of peasants; peasants in witch trials. The research is based on an interdisciplinary and phenomenological approach.

Funder

LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0026

Grant

LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0026

Researchers

Organizations
University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [MAGIC AND SUPERSTITION IN THE WORLDVIEW OF LATVIAN PEASANTS \(16TH–18TH CENTURIES\)](#)

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Researchers:

Organizations:

[University of Latvia](#)

Contact: [Bogdanovica Tatjana \(tatjana.bogdanovica@lu.lv\)](mailto:tatjana.bogdanovica@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0026](#)

Grants: [LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0026](#)

Project: [Cite Project](#)

3. License

License:

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2024-11-30](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Bibliography

List of scientific works on the topic of magic and superstition

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

To compile information about the state of research on the topic in Latvian and foreign historiography

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

3 Resources and Security

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Description of rituals in archival materials

Descriptions of rituals found in the archives of the Jesuit order have been translated into English and Latvian

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

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Statistics on the mention of different categories of rituals and superstitions

The statistics are collected from Jesuit reports and presented in the form of graphs.

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